

EXPLORING THE LUNAR SOUTH POLAR REGIONS WITH MOONIS ON RASHID ROVER 3.

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Introduction: MoonIS (Moon Infrared Spectrometer) is a VIS–NIR spectrometer (0.4–2.3 μm) selected for the *Emirates Lunar Mission* (ELM) of the Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre (MBRSC) [1]. The instrument will fly on board Rashid Rover 3, which targets exploration of the lunar South Pole region, with launch currently planned not earlier of 2029. MoonIS spectrometer is a heritage of the Ma_MISS instrument on board the Rosalind Franklin rover of the ESA ExoMars mission [2].

The mission aims to investigate the geology and mineralogy of the southern polar terrain, explore Permanently Shadowed Regions (PSRs), and characterize the presence and distribution of water ice and hydroxyl on and beneath the lunar surface.

Lunar PSRs: Lunar PSRs are among the most promising reservoirs of water ice in the inner Solar System and represent key targets for sustainable lunar exploration. These regions act as cold traps for volatiles delivered by cometary and asteroidal impacts, surface–solar wind interactions, and possible endogenic outgassing [3–7]. Despite detections of hydrogen-bearing species, the fine-scale geomorphology, physical state, and spatial distribution of ice within PSRs remain poorly constrained due to the limited spatial resolution and signal-to-noise ratio of current datasets [8–11]. Furthermore, it is not clear how much water ice on the Moon is exposed, since, from a morphological point of view, it does not present the expected characteristics [12–14].

In situ investigations are therefore essential to assess the abundance, distribution, and origin of lunar polar volatiles and to clarify their implications for the history of water in the Solar System. For this reason, several space agencies are planning to send rovers to better investigate water-ice and overall surface composition within PSRs and pave the way for human exploration.

The MoonIS instrument:

MoonIS is derived from the Ma_MISS instrument onboard ESA’s *ExoMars Rosalind Franklin* rover, with adaptations in the optical head, calibration target, thermomechanical configuration, and electronics to meet lunar environmental requirements. The optical head, mounted on the rover mast, is connected via optical fibers to the spectrometer unit housed within the rover body. Each fiber is coupled to a dedicated optical element and mapped onto the spectrometer slit, allowing simultaneous acquisition of multiple spatial elements (“pseudo-pixels”) and generation of hyperspectral images. MoonIS

Optical Head comprises of 3 elements. By scanning the scene through mast motion and rover displacement, MoonIS will characterize areas surrounding the rover, both in sunlit terrain and inside PSRs. An onboard illumination system will enable spectral measurements within permanently shadowed environments. An external calibration target is under consideration to ensure radiometric and spectral calibration accuracy.

The primary scientific objectives of MoonIS are to:

- Detect and discriminate between H₂O and OH-bearing materials;
- Quantify their abundance and spatial distribution;
- Map the mineralogy of the landing area.
- Identify major lunar rock classes;
- Detect and quantify key minerals (e.g., pyroxenes, olivines, feldspars, spinels);
- Characterize mineral mixtures and their spatial variability.

The instrument’s spectral range, resolution, signal-to-noise ratio, and spatial sampling are optimized to achieve these goals under both sunlit and permanently shadowed conditions. MoonIS will provide critical ground-truth measurements to advance our understanding of lunar polar volatiles and support future robotic and human exploration.

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